

Parenting and educating in mathematics: Parental engagement during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic

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In this symposium we engage participants in actively reflecting on our work with/as parents and caregivers in mathematics education and on their own experiences within their local contexts during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our goal is to reimagine parental engagement and plan for future collaborations to support new possibilities for and address exacerbated barriers to parental engagement in mathematics education.

Focus of the symposium

Parents' and caregivers' role in shaping children's mathematics education often goes overlooked, and the intersecting identities of mathematics teachers and teacher educators as parents is rarely considered. The COVID-19 pandemic, however, has placed parents in the spotlight. As nations aimed to slow the spread of the virus, 1.5 billion students worldwide abruptly transitioned to emergency remote mathematics instruction (UNESCO, 2020). A year later, the COVID-19 outbreak continues to cause significant disruptions to education. Parents have been thrust into unprecedented levels of engagement with school mathematics, and their responsibility for ensuring their child's mathematics learning has increased significantly. At the same time, as the work of educators has shifted into their homes, mathematics teachers and teacher educators are educating their students and parenting their children simultaneously.

Our intention for this symposium is to consider how COVID-19 might *enable* parental engagement by explicitly increasing expectations for involvement of parents in school mathematics and by drawing attention to the intersections of mathematics teaching and parenting. Symposium organizers will offer perspectives on parental engagement in mathematics during COVID-19 from two countries – the United States and New Zealand. By asking participants to reflect on our work with/as parents and on their own experiences in local contexts, we hope to build a global network of scholars committed to parental engagement and to plan for future collaborations.

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Parental engagement in mathematics education

Parents are uniquely positioned to support children's mathematics education across formal schooling. Unsurprisingly, parental involvement is strongly linked to children's mathematics achievement (Knapp et al., 2017). Yet, efforts to broaden mathematics learning opportunities largely ignore parents, which pits schools, teachers, and parents against each other rather than fostering partnerships for learning. Differences between parents' own mathematics education, which likely emphasized rules and procedures (Jackson & Remillard, 2005), and the curriculum and instruction experienced by their children present barriers to parental involvement, even in early grade levels (Muir, 2012). This challenge was intensified by the pandemic as parents struggled with or resisted the continuation of mathematical reasoning through child-centered strategies when learning shifted into the home. Despite these challenges, we see potential in blurring the line between parenting and educating in mathematics and seek to imagine possibilities for parental engagement. To that end, we ask questions such as:

3. What were the experiences of parents in diverse local contexts during the initial transition to emergency remote instruction? Presently?
4. How can we (re)envision parental engagement in mathematics education? How can we spark and sustain such efforts to engage parents in our local contexts?
5. How have parent experiences with mathematics education during the global pandemic created new barriers to engagement? How might we address those?

Symposium structure

After an overview (5 minutes), each organizer will present key ideas from their work with/as parents (20 minutes). Then, participants will engage in an interactive session to reflect on the experiences of parents with mathematics education in their local contexts in relation to the questions raised (40 minutes). We will conclude by building visions for parental engagement and planning for future collaborations (25 minutes).

Piata Allen and **Tony Trinick** both lecture at the University of Auckland where they focus on Māori-medium mathematics education. COVID-19 impacted differently on Māori-medium schools and whanau (extended families) than English-medium in Aotearoa New Zealand. This was in part due to the historic legacy of under resourcing of Māori-medium education by the State, in digital, human and print resources since the emergence of Māori-medium education 40 years ago. We discuss, our experiences as teacher educators, professional development facilitators and, in the case of Piata, a Māori-medium parent to support teachers and schools to teach mathematics in the medium of te reo Māori (the Māori language) during COVID-19 school closures. Our findings indicate that Māori-medium schools due to their legacy of being self-reliant, used their own agency to ensure a modicum of continuity in mathematics learning programmes. This was supported by wider community led initiatives that utilised social media and community networks to create, distribute and share resources quickly and efficiently in the face of inadequate state support.

Lisa Darragh lectures at the University of Auckland and her main research interest relates to learner and teacher identity in mathematics education. She will present results from a recent study she conducted with Dr. Nike Franke during the first couple of months of the nationwide lockdown in April 2020. The survey invitation was sent via Facebook community groups around Aotearoa New Zealand and received 634 responses over a three-week period. Parents were generally very engaged in the home learning of mathematics. They reported a range of opinions about quality of mathematics work and teacher support, and there was a correlation between general stress levels and negative opinions. To further support their child's mathematics learning, many parents turned to online mathematics programs, about which they were very positive, but the crisis brought to the fore a number of pre-existing issues. We argue that these findings have implications for all forms of mathematics home learning in the future, and suggest that schools need to listen to parental feedback regarding the quality, level and quantity of mathematics work. Additionally, schools could consider ways to deliver effective teacher support and to foster parental agency in helping their children with mathematics learning.

Frances K. Harper is an assistant professor at the University of Tennessee, Knoxville, where she focuses on how parent-teacher-community partnerships shift traditional power dynamics in mathematics education. She will present findings from a recent study conducted with Dr. Joshua Rosenberg, Sara Comperry, Kay Howell, and Sierra Womble during the initial transition to emergency remote instruction in 2020. Examining 100 survey responses and over 200 posts from Twitter, we saw a commitment among parents to engaging children with a range of mathematics topics from the elementary/primary school curriculum and a strong desire for collaborations among parents and teachers. We argue that these findings have implications for how we renew efforts to engage parents, such as placing greater value on the authentic ways families already engage in mathematics in the home and inviting parents into conversations about school mathematics on social media or in other accessible spaces. Harper will share how these implications inform the ongoing development of two networks of parent-teacher-community partners in her current projects, namely, networks aimed at fostering computational thinking among Black and Latinx pre-schoolers and at advancing racial justice in elementary/primary mathematics.

Naomi Jessup is an assistant professor at Georgia State University and one of her research interests examines the impact of COVID-19 on mathematics teaching and learning for Black communities as well as rehumanizing and culturally responsive approaches by parents. She will present preliminary findings of an ongoing two-year study that examined how Black parents in the United States responded to supporting their children's elementary mathematics learning with resources provided by schools throughout the middle of the 2019-2020 school year and subsequent school year. Initial findings indicate a range of approaches and strategies used by Black parents given that many of the strategies desired for learning mathematics were not common to them. In addition, parents voiced frustrations regarding the quality, rigor, and lack of cultural responsiveness of the mathematics tasks provided. Some parents modified and adapted the mathematics resources provided by the school to

better accommodate their child's learning and allow them to make cultural and real-work connections. Parents discussed increased agency in supporting their child's mathematics learning and due to their shift in roles and responsibilities from pre-pandemic to now. Implications from this study provide a counternarrative regarding Black parents' engagement in their children's mathematics learning and highlights their social and cultural capital that is often not invited, noticed, or silenced in schools.

Mary Candace Raygoza is an assistant professor and STEMist teacher educator at Saint Mary's College of California. This presentation examines her mathematical motherscholar praxis during the COVID-19 pandemic and present global reckoning for racial justice. In March 2020, her child's pre-school closed, as schools far and wide shuttered for in-person instruction. Alongside her paid work, she was also an informal pre-school teacher of one pupil, joining many parents, especially mothers, around the world whose roles in relation to schooling shifted suddenly and with little societal support. Informed by scholarship that highlights how much young children know and can do mathematically (Johnson et al., 2019), the mathematics that emerges from play (Wager & Parks, 2014), and the potential to connect (in)justice issues to early childhood mathematics (Ward, 2017), she will explore lessons from her three-year-old, namely how her child led the way in revealing mathematics connected to social-emotional growth and as part of learning about fairness and solidarity (e.g., the mathematics that emerged out of a community circle of stuffed animals). As the presenter interrogates her privilege as a white woman and a mathematics teacher educator mother, she also wonders: How can we support parents and caregivers to feel affirmed that meaningful mathematics lives within activity that is not intentionally mathematical (and is something accessible to them and their participation); and how can schools shape mathematics teaching and learning with that in mind?

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